

‘The Missing Piece’ in Handwriting Instruction – A Problem of Practice

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Although it is the digital age, handwriting is still a predominant means of expression as it occupies considerable amount of school time and assessments are largely paper based. As much as there is empirical evidence of the far-reaching benefits of handwriting, research also asserts that handwriting is not a natural skill but needs to be trained as part of the literacy and writing instruction. Studies also reveal that handwriting instruction is not included as part of initial teacher training studies. Teachers are not informed of handwriting milestones and developmental prerequisites. This paper intends to review the literature and delve deeper into my problem of practice as a paediatric occupational therapist. In addition to emphasising the importance of handwriting instruction, this paper also examines the handwriting related components of the National Curriculum of England (2014). Although the national curriculum outlines statutory handwriting requirements for the primary years, it does not provide teachers with a research-informed handwriting curriculum or the necessary training to implement one effectively. This ‘missing piece’ reflects serious consequences at micro, meso and macro levels, as failure to attain handwriting competency during the primary school years often impacts on both academic success and self-esteem. Studies have suggested that handwriting instruction is best achieved by an interdisciplinary approach involving Occupational Therapy and Education. Accordingly, this paper aims to examine key literature that must be considered when designing an interdisciplinary intervention to provide teacher professional learning in handwriting instruction, thereby helping to address the gap in my problem of practice.

Keywords: Handwriting Instruction, Occupational Therapy

Highlights

- Handwriting is not part of the initial teacher education which leaves most of the teachers uninformed about how to nurture this skill and handle further challenges (Ofsted, 2017).
- Keyboarding cannot be substituted for handwriting as the latter is a pre-requisite for the former. This implies that handwriting fluency is a requirement to achieve keyboarding fluency and speed (Connelly, Gee and Walsh, 2007).
- Handwriting training is best achieved by an inter-disciplinary approach between Occupational Therapy (OT) and Educational studies, where the occupational therapist reflects on the handwriting instruction and imparts teacher training apart from addressing the therapeutic needs (Lee *et al.*, 2022).

Introduction

Handwriting is important for psychomotor development, creativity and gaining self-confidence (Chicu, Țicău and Șoitu, 2014). Handwriting difficulties affect between 10-30% of school-aged children which do not resolve without intervention (Feder and Majnemer, 2007). Hence, teachers training this skill should be adequately equipped to impart the instruction based on developmental principles (Graham *et al.* 2008; Dockrell, Marshall and Wyse, 2016). Research has asserted that no matter how far technology takes us in the future, handwriting cannot be replaced by keyboarding as the former leads to the latter (Freeman, Mackinnon and Miller, 2005; Stevenson and Just, 2014). Therefore, handwriting will remain as a basic hand skill to be trained, and robust instruction is key to developing this skill. On the other hand, the lack of teacher training in handwriting instruction (Graham *et al.*, 2008; Chicu, Țicău and Șoitu, 2014; Nye and Sood, 2018) seems to leave teachers unaware of the handwriting developmental stages, proper grip patterns, biomechanical factors and letter formations. This often leads to children left uncorrected who end up repeating 'wrong' practices that become ingrained as wrong habits over time. Furthermore, teachers find it challenging to unlock the writing motivation when confronted with neurodiverse population in inclusive classrooms, thereby leaving a vast majority of them being referred to Occupational Therapy (OT) (Feder, Majnemer and Synnes, 2000; Asher, 2006). Hence, the lack of teacher education in handwriting instruction is both a real-life problem and a problem of practice. This paper will examine these ideas in more detail and relate them to the researcher's own experiences.

Is Handwriting an important skill even in this digital age?

Handwriting is a complex skill involving deep-laden neurological processes (Feder and Majnemer, 2007). The fine and intricate movements of the hand involved in the mere physical act of shaping letters activates the motor memory in the sensorimotor zones of the brain. This results in the formation of more complex neural network connectivity in the alpha bands corresponding to long-term memory and theta bands related to working memory and novel learning. Keyboarding or typewriting does not yield this as it does not involve the intricate hand movements but only a simple key press to produce the entire wanted form (Van Der Weel and Van Der Meer, 2024).

Studies have also proven that the use of only one hand slows down the process of writing giving more time to reflect, process information and consequently leading to better memory and retention compared to keyboarding which goes faster and does not provide enough time for absorption (Berninger *et al.*, 2009; Mangen and Velay, 2010; Alonso, 2015). Hence, the brain engages differently when we write something by hand as opposed to typing

and owing to this deeper engagement, writing by hand rather than typing yields higher quality in terms of factual, conceptual, and inferential aspects (Mueller and Oppenheimer, 2014). Upon examining the efficacy of handwriting with pencil against keyboarding or writing with stylus on a tablet, it was proven that handwriting with pencil fosters acquisition of letter knowledge and improves visuo-spatial skills compared to keyboarding. Additionally, using a stylus on a slippery tablet surface imposes high demands on motor control which produces poorly written letters, which might compromise the quality of motor and visual memory trace (Mayer *et al.*, 2020).

Despite these important findings, studies do not exclude keyboarding in the digital classrooms, rather caution against replacing handwriting entirely and employing keyboarding strategically based on task requirements (Alonso, 2015; Van Der Weel and Van Der Meer, 2024). Motor learning principles emphasise that well developed handwriting skill precedes keyboarding skill and facilitates speed eventually (Freeman, Mackinnon and Miller, 2005; Connelly, Gee and Walsh, 2007; Stevenson and Just, 2014). Handwriting fluency is a strong indicator of keyboarding fluency, or in other words, those with handwriting difficulties often struggle with typing speed (Connelly, Gee and Walsh, 2007). Based on the provided research, handwriting is considered a more fundamental process than typewriting. The ongoing shift from handwriting to typewriting in educational settings is a concern, as it could negatively impact the learning process (Van Der Weel and Van Der Meer, 2024). The benefits of handwriting are extensive, ranging from early literacy skills to overall school achievement and self-esteem (Chicu, Țicău, and Șoitu, 2014). Consequently, despite advancements in technology, research suggests that penmanship will continue to be a foundational hand skill for humans to master.

The importance of handwriting instruction as part of Initial Teacher Training (ITT)

Handwriting is a complex skill that is not innate but must be trained by making it a part of the writing and literacy instruction (Datchuk, 2016). UNESCO (1948) recommended to the Ministries Of Education concerning the teaching of handwriting and stressed that it should be a constant concern of school authorities and educationists and that teachers should be trained to give a rationale teaching of handwriting. The meta-analysis study by Santangelo and Graham (2016) showed the impressive impact of handwriting instruction on writing quality, length, fluency and legibility. On the contrary, handwriting is not a focused area in formal teacher training studies. For example, the study by Graham *et al.*, (2008) in the United States showed that only 12% of teachers indicated that the education courses taken in college

adequately prepared them to teach handwriting. Drawing closer to home, in the Ofsted (2017) report in England, school leaders reported that only 17% of the Newly Qualified Teachers were particularly well trained in Transcription skills which are Spelling and Handwriting. The following two observations concerning handwriting practice time in classrooms and prevalence rates of handwriting difficulties highlight the importance of teacher education in handwriting instruction:

1. Handwriting practice time in classrooms - The study (McHale and Cermak, 1992) reported that 31-60% of a school day is occupied by fine motor activities in kindergarten and primary school out of which 85% of fine motor activities involved paper and pencil tasks. Caramia et al. (2020) conducted a replication study revealing that while students spent the same total amount of time on fine motor tasks, the time dedicated specifically to writing, colouring, and drawing decreased significantly, ranging from 17.8% to 37.4% across grades. One of the reasons for not being able to create ample opportunities of handwriting practice in the classroom could be owed to the lack of training and resources, as explained by teachers (Graham *et al.*, 2008; Chicu, Țicău and Șoitu, 2014; Dockrell, Marshall and Wyse, 2016; Nye and Sood, 2018, Ofsted, 2024).
2. Prevalence rates of handwriting difficulties - While some studies (Feder and Majnemer, 2007; Chung, Patel and Nizami, 2020) show that handwriting difficulties affect between 10-30% of school-aged children, few other studies (Karlsdottir and Stefansson, 2002; Overvelde and Hulstijn, 2011) mention 5-33% as the prevalence rate. Although the prevalence rates across these studies are around the same range it is still a wide range and the simple explanation behind this being the timing of the testing. Studies by Karlsdottir and Stefansson (2002) and Overvelde and Hulstijn (2011) show that handwriting improves longitudinally during primary school, emphasizing the teacher's role in fostering penmanship. Additionally, early identification and targeted remedial instruction significantly improve handwriting difficulties across these years.

'The missing piece' in handwriting instruction – Problem of Practice Unveiled

The compelling evidence from research identifies the missing piece in handwriting instruction as the lack of teacher training and research-based curriculum which is both a real-life problem and a problem of practice. As handwriting has not been a focused area in the formal teacher training studies, most of the teachers are not aware of the handwriting developmental stages or ways to nurture the fundamental developmental components like, fine motor skills, visual motor integration, visual perception and eye-hand coordination, to

name a few. Furthermore, this lack of awareness also impacts on inculcating proper grip patterns (rather correcting the atypical patterns sooner than later), teaching correct letter formations based on researched methods and ensuring pre-requisites like posture, paper angulation and so on.

Global studies as cited above have provided empirical evidence as how teachers felt uncomfortable teaching handwriting as they received either no training or informal training in handwriting instruction. Graham et al (2008) mentioned that by using a variety of recommended instructional practices for teaching handwriting, concerns were raised about the quality of handwriting instruction for all children. Teachers find it difficult to align teaching practices across classrooms and schools, leading to inconsistencies. Additionally, children are not provided with ample opportunities to practice handwriting as it is often restricted to phonics lessons (Ofsted, 2024). In the same vein, Graham et al (2008) already stated that 93% of teachers felt that handwriting should be taught as a separate subject. Teachers have mentioned (Nye and Sood, 2018) about gaps in their knowledge base relating to developmental progression, ability to assist struggling students, awareness of strategies to use, and how the process of Individualized Education Plans (IEP) contributed to their challenges in teaching handwriting to kindergarten students. Many times, educational professionals or school psychologists suggest keyboarding as an accommodation to ease the frustration, but research has established that this itself cannot be of help as handwriting fluency is a prerequisite for keyboarding fluency (Freeman, Mackinnon and Miller, 2005; Connelly, Gee and Walsh, 2007; Stevenson and Just, 2014). On the other hand, a vast majority of them end up being referred to OT (Feder, Majnemer and Synnes, 2000; Asher, 2006), where most often only a few children among the referrals require therapeutic intervention.

Figure 1 - Praxis in handwriting instruction

Researcher Positionality

Handwriting is one of the core areas addressed by OTs, especially in a school-based practice (Asher, 2006; Nye and Sood, 2018). Handwriting instruction is best achieved by an interdisciplinary approach between OT and Educational studies as it involves many underlying factors, like, neuromotor developmental, ergonomic, cognitive and orthographic factors (Lee *et al.*, 2022). Stevenson and Just (2014) suggested the use of the OT consultative model at the continuing education and university level teacher education programs to facilitate an understanding of motor learning and age-appropriate expectations. This is also evidenced by teachers indicating that they would like to have a curriculum that included formal training that is specifically provided by the OT and the need to develop a collaborative service delivery model in which an OT serves as a coach to the teachers (Nye and Sood, 2018). Leveraging my experience as a paediatric OT, I consult for various international and European schools in Belgium. My work focuses on delivering handwriting interventions for students of all ages and empowering teachers with case-specific insights.

National Curriculum of England 2014 (hereafter, NC2014) – Handwriting goes under the radar!

As an OT supporting children in international and European schools in Belgium, the initial phase of this study involved analysing the curricula adopted by these institutions. This paper focuses primarily on the National Curriculum 2014 (NC2014), as it is the standard for most British international schools in the region and is central to my problem of practice. Consequently, the curriculum of the English section of the European Schools is outside the scope of this paper and will be analysed in a subsequent phase of the study. While the NC2014 (DfE, 2014) comprises broad aims and programmes of study across key stages, this analysis concentrates exclusively on the handwriting requirements found under the 'Transcription' subdomain of 'Writing'.

Although the NC2014 states the statutory requirements for handwriting achievement, it does not provide a curricular pathway or pedagogical information around handwriting development in children. Despite its strengths, the curriculum lagged in the following three areas -

1. Curriculum coherence – As it did not provide a curricular pathway, schools were forced to create their own handwriting policies leading to inconsistencies.
2. Developmental approach and struggling writers - Handwriting does not develop naturally for elementary-aged students (Datchuk, 2016). It is an effortful skill (Graham *et al.*, 2008)

that must be trained alongside the child's development, considering the age and stage of handwriting development. Early intervention is key in this process to help children in their primary school years so that writing becomes an automatic process in the post-primary years. Therefore, a developmental teaching approach is required (Sassoon, 2003) as the time spent learning and engaging in handwriting is important to overall writing development (Datchuk, 2016). The absence of training and resources for handwriting instruction within the curriculum left teachers knowledge-deficient with regards to motor skill development or handwriting milestones. This is crucial for teachers to set grade-specific handwriting objectives (Chicu, Țicău and Șoitu, 2014) and furthermore, supporting struggling writers.

3. Less emphasised – Handwriting being a motor skill is best learned via spaced practice, like several times a week or daily (Graham *et al.*, 2008). But the national curriculum hardly gives any time-specifics or exclusive opportunities for handwriting practice leaving letter formations to be taught only in phonics lessons (Ofsted, 2024).

The above weaknesses not only created an implementation gap but impacted at the National, School and Classroom levels.

Impact - Macro, Meso and Micro

The lack of a research-informed national curriculum and teacher education in handwriting led schools to develop their own handwriting policies and diverse instructional approaches. This autonomy created inconsistencies and confusion, for example, the debate over introducing cursive from the start or at a developmentally appropriate stage (Smits, 2016). Additionally, the curriculum does not even specify a particular font style but leaves only some guidance notes, which has been ignored by many schools again leading to inconsistencies. At the classroom level, significant issues persisted as teachers found it challenging to provide handwriting instruction owing to lack of specific training, absence of clear guidance on the frequency and intensity of handwriting activities and sustained confusion over effective methods. Ofsted (2022) emphasises on 'repeated practice', conversely, it is important to repeat the 'right' practice than ingraining the wrong habits, which is achievable when teachers are formally educated in this area. Furthermore, handwriting is assessed within broader statutory assessments and not as a distinct skill, with evaluations left to teachers' discretion which apart from making it subjective, also remains questionable against their level of training. This situation at one point also contributed to the amplification of special needs and increase in the number of referrals.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the compelling evidence from research and practice identify the 'missing piece' as the need for a research-based curriculum and teacher education in handwriting instruction. It may even be essential to include specialist practitioners to develop the handwriting curriculum and professional learning for teachers. Asher in her study in 2006 drew attention to the practical issue of OTs receiving a myriad of referrals for handwriting intervention especially in a school-based setting. The literature review not only holds true in the global scenario but equally impacts in my practice as well.

Asher's (2006) study suggested that OTs need to reflect on the initial instruction of handwriting imparted by educators, in addition to addressing the therapeutic needs. By contributing to the effectiveness of the initial handwriting instruction and teacher education, OTs can then ensure that all students receive proper instruction which will then leave only those students who have genuine deficits to be directed towards therapeutic intervention. When classroom handwriting instruction aligns with OT strategies, it not only stays consistent but also makes it much easier to spot specific skill deficits—like casting a line into crystal-clear water! Moving forward, this study will examine the curriculum of the English section of the European Schools in Belgium. The objective is to develop a targeted professional learning program that empowers primary school teachers with both developmental knowledge and a research-informed framework for handwriting instruction. By addressing this 'missing piece' in current practice, this research aspires to serve as a foundational evidence base for policymakers and curriculum designers.

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